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MASTER'S THESIS**

COMPUTER SCIENCE IN URBAN K-8 SCHOOLS

By:

Wilma Ann Anderson

APPROVED:

Thesis Advisor

Chairperson, EDTC Department

Dean, College of Education

Date Filed

Advisor: Dr. Sofia Levchak

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Wilma Ann Anderson

Educational Technology Department

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Abstract

In this study, the researcher assessed the level of computer science familiarity of elementary and middle school age children in two schools in an urban school district in New Jersey. As a method of conducting this research study, the researcher chose action-based research. A survey was designed for this study to identify computer science familiarity and knowledge base of elementary and middle school students. This survey was designed to elicit detailed information regarding K-8 students' acquisition of computer science skills and perceptions on careers in technology fields. As a basis for questions to include in the survey, the researcher relied on questions included in related past studies, information from computer science professionals, and Jersey City Public Schools Supervisors of related fields. The researcher is a certified teacher, who taught a computer coding class through an afterschool program at School A using the Code.org curriculum. The researcher was trained to use this curriculum in 2015. Participation in the survey was voluntary and it was disseminated before the instructional day to a random sample of 100 students at each school.

Key words: computer science, STEM, coding, urban

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Chapter I. The Problem and Its Setting

Background

As our society increasingly develops as a digital environment, every aspect of our lives is becoming digitized. This, in turn, has increased the need for a qualified workforce—one that is trained with digital skills. Diversity in the workforce has been a conversation since the days of the Civil Rights Movement. Additionally, the conversation on gender diversity emerged during the Women’s Suffrage Movement. While our society still struggles to fully equalize the pay scale of women who have already broken the gender barrier and thrive in traditionally male-dominated professions, women face another challenge: the disproportionate number of women in technology fields. The future of women in technology fields has not only to do with adequate training, aptitude and access, but also to do with the social ramifications of the new technologies because the relationship of women and technology is a social one (Cianni & Weitz, 1986).

Girls are introduced to career choices through family, the media, community interactions (e.g., church and community programs), and school. Educators have a unique opportunity to shape career choices. For many youth, conversations about careers *only* occur with educators. These educators often serve as mentors and mentoring is a viable way to encourage girls into computer technologies (Pisimisi & Ionnides, 2005). Rudnick and Wallach (1980) assert that educators are responsible for encouraging young women to expand their career horizons. By the time they must choose careers, girls have less experience with computers and perceive that they are lagging behind boys (AAUW,

2009). In fact, the organization posits that without proper intervention strategies, many women will never become computer professionals. This issue is not unique to the United States. London's Science and Technology Facilities Council, launched at the Science Museum in London, pledged, in 2014, its support to get more women into science and technology careers through the British government's Your Life Campaign.

The Science and Technology Facilities Council pledged to run public events to engage girls and women, run school activities to engage with girls directly and indirectly and review and make improvements with how girls interacted with Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math (STEM) (Education Journal, 2014). Efforts in the United States have been increased to match such initiatives. Code.org is one such organization hosting a global effort that encourages educators across the nation to teach code to youth of both genders by way of the annual event Hour of Code. The National Center for Women & Information Technology (NCWIT) leads various initiatives that investigate the role of females in information technology. Compugirls, an organization at Arizona State University, was part of an NCWIT case study that moved beyond the discussion of girls in technology to a discussion about culturally responsive computing.

Through the surveying of approximately 200 boys and girls in the fourth through eighth grades, data reflecting 1. awareness of the definition of computer science; 2. attitudes about careers in computer science; 3. perceptions about technology jobs being suited for males and/or females and; 4. and the importance of computer science versus core content area subjects was collected.

Purpose

The purpose of this action-based research was to unearth data that exist on women in technology fields and reveal the perceptions of elementary and middle school age children in two schools in an urban school district in New Jersey about computer science. Methods by which our society is currently encouraging girls to enter technology fields are discussed, and the researcher makes suggestions on how to improve these efforts. The study highlights the teaching of computer coding in the K-8 environment as one entry point. Collected data assessed the current efforts of the urban educational and social environment in which the students learn and live and determined where access points to technology fields lie for urban youth. The research included a coding class taught by the researcher and the students served as participants in the action research.

The researcher will share findings with the Chief Academic Officer of Jersey City Public Schools and members of the Curriculum and Instruction Department with the goal of sparking the full integration of computer science content into the K-8 curriculum.

Research Questions

1. What role does computer science play in the lives of urban K-8 students?
2. What are the perceptions of urban K-8 students about computer science and its gender association?
3. Are the perceptions of urban K-8 female students a predictor of the number of women entering computer science fields due to the offering of computer science in K-8 learning environment?

Need for the Study

American society needs to prepare youth for the digital workforce. As males are more likely to enter technological fields (AAUW, 2009), our society must make a concerted effort to recruit and train a female candidate pool and subsequently include females in this sector of the workforce. This study will be a resource to educators and those involved in policy affecting education. Stakeholders in the education of youth can use this study to critically analyze where our society currently stands as it regards staffing current technology positions; training youth in technological fields; and being purposeful in encouraging females to enter fields with mastery of computer science as the foundation.

Definitions

Computer science:

New Jersey Institute of Technology (2017) defines computer science as a discipline that involves the design and development of computing systems applications and their effective deployment and use. It ranges from theoretical studies of algorithms to practical problems of system implementation involving both software and hardware.

Summary

The purpose of this action research study was to identify the perceptions of urban elementary and middle school students about careers in technology, and examine how early introduction to computer science and coding can positively affect career choice. The research highlighted early exposure as a means to increase the number of females entering technology careers.

In Chapter II, the review of literature examines these topics through the lenses of: Feminist Theory, Diversity in the Workforce, and Developing Entrance Strategies for girls to approach careers in technology fields.

Chapter II. Review of Related Literature

In conducting this study, the researcher relied on many sources. Peer-reviewed articles from educational journals, white papers completed by women in technology advocacy groups and professional organizations, and studies done on women in technology. Research was conducted using databases available through the Frank J. Guarini Library of New Jersey City University, and on the World Wide Web. The researched material fell into three categories: Feminist Theory, Diversity in the Workforce, and Developing Entrance Strategies.

Feminist Theory

The idea that women should be part of technology is not a new one. As women are users of technology, they should be creators and designers of technology as well. Modern society has demonstrated comfortability with this fact and structures exist so women can enter and thrive in technology fields. The issue is that the rate at which this gender integration is happening is slow. Feminists argue that there are varied discriminatory reasons for this (Rosser, 2005). Liberal feminists demand that everyone receives equal opportunity, regardless of gender. They seek to equalize the workforce when it comes to distribution of workers based on gender. They fight to have women be equally involved in the design of technology and processes, and seek to equalize access and use of technology (Rosser, 2005). The deeper into policymaking these efforts go so that policy effects change in K-12 schools, the higher the likelihood of young women entering technology fields.

Social feminists are poised to deconstruct women's contributions in technology as ones that "reinforce patriarchy and power differentials in the home" (Rosser, 2005, p. 3). These feminists want women to not only work less on tedious, eye-straining assembly lines, but they rally for women to have more access to funds, so they may launch technology start-ups and thrive financially from boardroom positions. Ramilo (2006) maintains that the challenge for women is to not only manage the technologies, but also to create them. Social feminists' position on use of technology is a position based on social class and the opportunity that higher social class affords those who design and use technology. They say taxpayers' money funds high-stakes technology initiatives, but capitalist interests outweigh public needs (Rosser, 2005).

From the 1950s through the 1970s, technology in the workplace for women was summed up in two words: clerical jobs. The typewriter was a piece of equipment that shaped the role of women in the workforce. Women were marketed to with flowery-designed typewriters, and television ads placed typewriters in middle-class homes even though the typewriter was office equipment (Boyer & England, 2008). This workforce dynamic was challenged as women voiced opposition to the picture being painted of women office workers as simply extensions to typewriters. Women were acknowledging the limitations of clerical jobs, and new technologies offered a shifting identity. As older technologies faded out of the spotlight, jobs in different settings, such as banks, increased for women, offering them opportunities to master new technology skills.

Banks later, in a cost-cutting move, reduced its teller staff and introduced the Automatic Teller Machine (ATM). In order to do so effectively, the ATMs used a woman's voice to appear less threatening and user friendly (Boyer & England, 2008).

Modern-day “Siri,” launched by Apple for its iPhone, is the non-threatening authoritative voice of new information. Siri’s reach is global, depth of knowledge near infinite, and uses are from everyday practical to scientifically specific. Siri is even used in laboratories to shrink the time needed to find information and possibly enhance lab activities for students with visual or motor skill disabilities (Brunsell & Horejsi, 2013). The default voice is female and can be changed via the device’s settings. Increasingly, the voice of technology is female—but this growth is slow.

Diversity in the Technology Workforce

Hispanics and Blacks face specific challenges when it comes to access to technology career opportunities. According to the National Science Foundation (NSF), (2017), “a smaller proportion of Blacks are in Science and Engineering occupations than are in the U.S. workforce as a whole (5% versus 12%)” (p. 12). The percentage for Hispanics is six percent versus sixteen percent (NSF, 2017). The youth of these ethnic groups may be in lower-performing urban areas that do not have the resources needed to teach technology skills. Computer science, for example, needs to be taught on a computer for full acquisition of skills, practice, and innovation. Not all urban schools have enough adequate computers.

Code.org has created free curriculum and professional development for teachers to bring coding to their schools, regardless of the socio-economic status of the teacher’s district. While there are “unplugged” activities that teach the science of coding without the need for computers, true acquisition of the skills comes with full access to the technology. A 2015 Gallup poll revealed that exposure to computer technology is the gateway to building confidence, but Black and Hispanic students are less likely than

White students to have an adult in their life that works with computers or technology.

Having family members who work in a specific field, often bring exposure to that field for youth. The study found that Hispanics have less access to Internet access at home than Black or Whites, and lower-income students and Blacks have the least access.

While some youth have families that include women who work in a technological capacity, Rosser (2005) asserts that women of color occupy high health-risk assembly jobs in technology in high numbers, and are less represented as decision makers and less considered as users. Those at higher levels in academia are few. A 2009 AAUW study revealed that women were grossly underrepresented in the doctoral faculty level. Of more than 7,000 computer science doctoral faculty in 2006, only 60 were Black women. The study further revealed that numbers for Hispanic and Native American women were too low to report.

Developing Entrance Strategies to Technology Careers

Dame Wendy Hall, Dean of the Faculty of Physical and Applied Sciences and a professor of computer science at the University of South Hampton says a career in engineering “isn’t there for the taking for women who want it” (Hall, 2013, p. 27). She asserts that women are not being encouraged “to think of technology as a career when they are making their choices at school” (Hall, 2013, p. 27). The classroom has to be woman friendly (Washburn, 2004). In order for young women to be attracted to technology fields, they need to be shown how their innate interests marry work being conducted in technology fields. When they reach college campuses, they need to see women role models in teaching and leadership positions, and the learning environment in which they are to spend their college years need to be welcoming. Washburn (2004) says

that the “absence of women faculty members and mentors both within the classroom and outside of it...and supportive networks can create a chilly climate for women in nontraditional fields” (p. 156).

The burden lies on the university and professors to construct a door to technology that women feel comfortable walking through and a learning environment in which women feel at home. Before girls reach higher education, there is opportunity to cultivate a generation of women through many strategies, mentoring being one of them. Pisimisi & Ionnides (2005) state, “[Mentors must be flexible], ready to give more opportunities to their protégés than simply technical knowledge” (p. 479). Pisimisi & Ionnides list professional status, social skills, previous training experience, and age as factors that contribute to effective mentoring relationships.

Early exposure and access is not prevalent with minority youth, though it may seem that as digital natives (Prensky, 2001) they are always sitting on the cusp of, and sometimes driving the design of, new technologies. Selwyn (2012) uses social theory to analyze the “structures, actions, processes, and relations that constitute uses of digital technology in educational setting and contexts” (p. 82). At the same time, the culture of technology in which groups of youth distinguished by demographic location and class must be analyzed. Simply put, the ‘Who’ and ‘Where’ affect the ‘What’ and the ‘How’ when it comes to understanding the ‘Why’ of the existing disparity of youth and technology, urban females in particular.

The AAUW released a study on the number of women in STEM careers. In the study, the metaphor of early exposure and access (entering the pipeline) for girls in

elementary schools and middle schools means increased numbers of female scientists and engineers (exiting the pipeline).

Summary

In conclusion, the review of literature fell into three categories: Feminist Theory, Diversity in the Workforce, and Developing Entrance Strategies. Women's view of themselves and their role in technology as consumers and developers has evolved, but not uniformly. The additional factor of race further creates a barrier to women entering and staying in technology careers. Chapter III will discuss the method by which the researcher collected data for the study.

Chapter III. Methodology

Research Methods

In this study, the researcher surveyed students to determine the level of computer science familiarity by elementary and middle school age children in the urban school district of Jersey City, NJ. This information was then analyzed and discussed.

Dissemination included a proposal to the Chief Academic Officer of Jersey City Public Schools, and to the Curriculum and Instruction Department. Focusing on entrance strategies for urban youth into the computer science field, this study's goal was to lay groundwork for curriculum development and district initiative in the field of computer science technology. Ultimately, the research was intended to enhance awareness and promote the teaching of computer science content in the elementary and middle schools of Jersey City.

As a method of conducting this research study, the researcher chose action-based research. Action-research, according to Sagor (2000), is defined as is a disciplined process of inquiry conducted by and for those taking the action.

Documents Used in the Study

Upon IRB approval (Appendix A), a letter requesting approval to conduct the study (Appendix B) was sent to the building principals of School A and School B. School district approval (Appendix C) followed and letters of consent (Appendix D) were collected from all parents of the student participants. The survey used in this study (Appendix E) was designed to elicit detailed information regarding K-8 students'

acquisition of computer science skills and perceptions on careers in technology fields.

The non-demographical questions asked students about their access to computer technology, computer science learning opportunities, their belief about the gender association of technology jobs, and the role technology would play in their future careers.

Resources

As a basis for questions to include in the survey, the researcher relied on questions included in related past studies, computer science professionals, Jersey City Public Schools curriculum and instruction supervisors, Jersey City Public Schools Supervisor of Educational Technology, and the researcher's academic advisor, Dr. Laura Zieger, before it was sent to the schools for dissemination. Research was conducted using databases available through the Frank J. Guarini Library of New Jersey City University, and on the World Wide Web. Survey data was inputted using Google Forms.

Participants

Participants from School A included students in Grade 3 through Grade 5. A random selection came from the school's 51% female population and the 49% male population. Eighty-two percent of the student body was considered economically disadvantaged. Participants from School B included students in Grade 6 through Grade 8. A random selection from the school's 44% female population and the 56% male population. Eighty-two percent of the student body was considered economically disadvantaged.

Data Collection

Blank surveys and the request letter were delivered to the principals of School A and School B for review. After approval was given by the Principal of School A, the

Assistant Principal approved the dissemination of the survey to students in Grade 3 through Grade 5 within the School A. The researcher hand delivered the surveys to teachers of these grade levels with instructions to allow students time before the instructional day began to complete the survey. Considering prior assignments and activities, the researcher asked teachers to choose a day during that week when the students might have the best focus. The Principal of School B approved the dissemination of the survey by the researcher to students in Grades 6 through Grade 8 in School B. In preparation, the researcher discussed the upcoming survey with each teacher several days before distribution took place. The survey was then hand delivered to teachers of Grades 6 through Grade 8 with instructions to allow students time before the instructional day began to complete the survey.

The researcher was in contact with the Assistant Principal of School A one week after the dissemination of the survey for review. The surveys had been secured by the classroom teachers until then. The researcher collected the surveys prior to the start of the school day. Collection of completed surveys was immediate at School B, just before the start of the school day. Participation in the survey was voluntary.

Data Analysis

Materials were analyzed for frequency of responses in each area. The frequency of responses to survey questions laid the groundwork for district-level, and school-level discussions about creating opportunities to integrate computer science into content area curricula within elementary and middle school classrooms and programs.

Procedures for analyzing materials included a tally. The tally or frequency count is the calculation of how many people fit into a given category or the number of times a

characteristic occurs. This calculation is expressed by both the absolute (actual number) and relative (percentage) totals (Southwest Missouri website). Frequency counts were applied to each question of the survey to determine similarities and differences among participants, and their individual gender. The survey also contained a section for the respondent to reply to a version of research question number one. Upon completion of the analysis of the data, results were compiled as to how to best integrate computer science education into the elementary and middle school curricula.

Summary

In Chapter III, the method used to conduct research was discussed. Copies of the survey and a request letter was delivered to an elementary school principal and to a middle school principal. The survey was administered and resulting data was collected and analyzed. In Chapter IV, a review of the responses from the returned surveys will be examined for the findings. The results from students will be analyzed for similarities and differences and then tabulated.

Chapter IV. Findings

The presentation of the data is the first section of this chapter. The goal was to present the data with fidelity and clarity. Presentation of the data reveals the results of the survey administered to Grades 3 through Grade 8 students in two urban, Jersey City, NJ schools. Their basic demographics, their perceptions of computer science and its role in school, and in the world, was presented. Next, a grouping of the results by category was created. The researcher encountered some challenges with data collection. Some teachers had not handed out the surveys to all students during the requested window. Some surveys had to be readministered because students had written their names on the survey. After those issues were addressed, the raw data was able to be entered into Google Forms which generated graphs and a spreadsheet.

Data Categorization

The purpose of this action research was to gather data that may be used to establish and tailor programs in urban K-8 schools that expose more female students to career pathways in computer science. In order to properly tailor programs to students, an assessment of their knowledge base and perceptions was necessary. This study may provide an assessment template that may be used by districts intending to integrate computer science across curricula offerings.

One hundred ninety students responded to the survey. The surveys were disseminated on paper. The researcher wanted to make sure attention was paid to the phrasing of the questions and eliminate the ease of clicking through to the next question.

Before the start of the instructional period, students received the survey from the homeroom teacher. Students in Grade 3 through Grade 8 completed the 16-question survey independently, with any phrases they did not understand being explained to them.

Figure 1. Prior Knowledge about Computer Science

Students were asked about their knowledge of computer science. Of the 190 students asked, 105 students, representing 55.3% of the respondents, indicated they were familiar with the definition of computer science. Eighty-five of the students, 47% of the respondents answered that they did not have any prior knowledge of computer science.

Figure 2. Weekly Computer Use at School

Students were asked how many times they used a computer at school during the school week. Thirty-three point seven percent of respondents indicated using a computer either three or four times a week and 33.7% indicated they use a computer five times a

week. Thirty-one point six percent used a computer one or two times a week and 1.1% used a computer between zero and two times a week.

Figure 3. Computer Science Class Content

For this question, students were allowed to select more than one response. The majority of respondents, 62.1%, cited they thought “programming” was what they might learn in a computer science class. “How computers work” garnered 58.9% of responses, with 112 students choosing this option. Eighty-three students, 43.7%, thought that advanced computer use would be learned in the class. “Networking” was selected by 80 students, 42.1% of total respondents and “computer repair” by 59 students, 31.1% of respondents. Forty-nine students, 25.8% indicated that “Internet use” is what they thought they would learn. Twenty-four students thought they would learn how to use social media. This was 12.6% of total students who took the survey. Thirty-two percent, 65 students, expected they would learn how to research.

Figure 4. The Importance of Computer Science vs. Core Courses

A minority of respondents, 8.5% (16 students), believed that computer science was not as important to learn as core courses like math, science, social studies and English. The majority: 123 respondents, 65.1%, thought computer science was just as important as core content area courses. Nineteen students, 10.1% thought computer science was more important than core courses.

Figure 5. Adults in Computer/Technology

Seventy-one respondents, 37.4% indicated that there is not an adult in their lives that works with computers or other types of technology. One hundred nineteen students, 62.6% of all respondents indicated that there was an adult in their lives who works with computers or other types of technology.

Figure 6. Positive Impact of Computer Science on Career

Seventy-seven-point four percent of respondents, 147 students, believed computer science can help them in their chosen career—22.6%, 43 students, did not. All students were asked, “What do you want to be when you grow up?” The careers listed by the 43 students were: chef, vet, football player, basketball player, baseball player, pastor, singer Physical Education teacher, dancer, cosmetologist, mechanic, movie director, hairstylist, model, actress, forensic scientist, policeman and, wrestler. These were cited as the careers in which students did not think computer science could play a role.

Data Discussion

The researcher found that the majority of students surveyed knew what computer science was and thought it would be useful somehow in the field they were interested in pursuing. The majority of students surveyed had contact with an adult who was in a technical career. One hundred thirty-eight students believed technology jobs to be male jobs and one hundred of the students indicated females, indicating an overlap of twenty-eight students who thought technology jobs should not be respective of any one gender.

Summary

In Chapter IV, the researcher discussed the findings of the questionnaires and how the data was organized. Questions were designed to allow students to either chose one answer or multiple answers. Additionally, students were presented with questions that allowed them to respond in short answer format. Students reported being able to access the Internet at school and on a device outside of school. Not all students were familiar with the term computer science, but the majority of students deemed it, inclusive with other technology fields, to be a male and female career pathway. Chapter V will analyze the findings relative to the research questions in Chapter II and discuss the implications.

Chapter V. Discussion

The purpose of this research study was to address the following questions:

1. What role does computer science play in the lives of urban K-8 students?
2. What are the perceptions of urban K-8 students about computer science and its gender association?
3. Are the perceptions of urban K-8 female students a predictor of the number of women entering computer science fields due to the offering of computer science in K-8 learning environment?

Knowledge of Computer Science

Research Question 1

What role does computer science play in the lives of urban K-8 students?

This study sought to explore the role of computer science in the lives of K-8 students in two schools in an urban New Jersey school district. From the data collected in response to the question “do you know what computers science is?”, the researcher determined that there was a 54%-46% split of urban students in K-8, in favor of those confirming prior knowledge of the definition of computer science. Computer science is not offered as a stand-alone course. Those students who do have exposure, may have exposure due to the efforts of individual teachers and media specialists, and through recent, annual school initiatives like the Hour of Code. Being able to access computer science content at school or outside of school is critical to learning the skills. Computer science in the 21st century plays a greater role in the lives of urban K-8 students than it

ever has. Former President Obama's 2013 call to action, "Don't just play on your phone—program it" is the sentiment of the movement to encourage students to shift the role computer science plays in their lives by being more than consumers.

Computer use. The researcher sought to explain that exposure to a computing device in school may impact a student's proclivity to enter a technology-based career. Two-thirds of students used a computer three to five times per week. This use was not disaggregated into what the computer was used for (word processing, Internet research, playing games, etc.) but focused more on access to the technology. This access is the gateway to developing technology skills. A 2015 survey by Code School echoed the benefits of early access to, and cultivation of technology skills. Gregg Pollack, founder and CEO of Code School, said of the 2015 survey of 2,200 coders and developers:

We conducted this survey to shine a light on what future coders and developers look like at a young age so we can identify budding computer scientists and cultivate their interests and talents early on...Understanding and identifying these traits and tendencies is important in helping parents, teachers and professionals prepare kids for potential future careers in the rapidly growing computer science and technology fields. (eweek.com, 2015, para. 5)

With one-third of respondents using computers zero to one time a week, the exposure to this career path may not be enough to spark sustained interest. Many elementary and middle school students may have personal devices such as cell phones or tablets that provide a different user experience when compared to the experience of using a laptop or computer. Using a computing device in the school setting in conjunction with academic work may provide a different user experience and promote interest in a setting

where learning is encouraged, and the device used is associated with a level of expected success.

There was a large disparity between the number of students who had adults in their lives who worked with computers and those who did not. This fact may impact the number of students pursuing a computer science field career. Children often emulate the adults in their lives. With 62.6% of respondents having the influence of a tech savvy adult in their lives, the chances of those students pursuing tech careers may be increased. This influence without access is less likely to produce progression into technology fields (Gallup, 2015). As students are encouraged through national testing of math and language arts through the PARCC assessment to excel in math and language arts, proponents of computer science urge that students are equally held to a high standard of achievement in computer science.

Importance of computer science. In asking students about their perceptions of the importance of computer science, the researcher sought to elicit a more critical, thoughtful response that revealed why students thought it is important. The data showed that two-thirds of students thought computer science was just as or more important than learning a core subject. Respondents demonstrated through this response that computer science has a place in their daily academic lives. An overwhelming 77.4% thought computers science would help them with their chosen careers. Students appeared to realize the pace of technology integration in the 21st century lives and how learning a technology-related subject would inform and prepare them in the same way core academic subjects do. Responses included:

- “[technology can help] by making us get better grades”
- “so you can use it in math and everything else”

- “Technology is a great thing. It can help you to do many things like coding. You can make your own websites or games or it could even help kids with do[ing] their homework like an online tutor and it could help you do many more great things. Technology can help you improve”
- “Technology can be used to make improvement by community, the world, in school, your brain, career, and by whatever you’re doing in your life”
- Technology gives students a fun way to learn. It can play a big part in engineering, which helps solves problems. Live robotic arms and cleaning robots that help people clean”
- “Technology can be used to make improvement by reading on the computer, doing math, science, spelling”

Out of one hundred ninety respondents, forty-one students did not think technology could help them in their careers. Sixty-one students did not think technology would make a difference in their school, community or world. Seventeen of these 61 were male, indicating that the majority of students who thought technology could make a difference and thought it would play a role in their careers were female.

Male or Female

Research Question 2

What are the perceptions of urban K-8 students about computer science and its gender association?

The researcher sought to demonstrate the perception students had about the gender association of computer science. While more students (138) thought technology jobs were inherently male jobs, a close number thought technology jobs were female (110) job; students were allowed to choose both male and female if they believed technology jobs could be equally performed by males and females. Only twenty-eight students indicated that technology jobs should not be assigned to a gender. This result may be a predictor that females and males who are educated in urban K-8 will enter technology jobs at a close rate in the next decade--the disparity we currently see should

disappear. Alba (2017) reported, “The field of computer science is growing so fast it outpaces all other occupations in the US” (para. 2). With a great push for girls to enter tech fields, this may be the reality of the near future.

With upwards of 60% of students surveyed expecting to learn programming in a computer science class, this and the other data suggest that more computer science content should be offered at the elementary and middle school levels. Students are aware of what it is and the majority have access to computers.

Women Entering Computer Science Fields

Research Question 3

Are the perceptions of urban K-8 female students a predictor of the number of women entering computer science fields due to the offering of computer science in K-8 learning environments?

Females are at a disadvantage, with the expectation that they will pursue technology jobs being lower than males, but the gap can be narrowed with increased awareness and support for females entering technology fields. Research by the US Department of Commerce (2011) reports that 30% of women were employed in STEM occupations in the year 2000, but the amount decreased to 27% by 2009. This decrease may be attributed several factors including to females not entering the field due to a lack of female role models in STEM (Hill, Corbett, St. Rose & AAUW, 2010) and females leaving the field due to not feeling supported. Ashcraft, Eger, & Friend, through the 2012 NCWIT study, *Girls in IT: The Facts*, posit that the perceptions of girls “...are shaped by the larger society and local environments in which they learn about computing and technology, and this significantly influences what appears to be their “choices” to pursue

computing and careers” (p. 17). Dasgupta and Stout (2014) found that “in middle and high school, mothers’ (more than fathers’) support predicts adolescent girls’ motivation” (p. 22).

Brandt (2014) states, “The middle school years have been shown to be important developmental stepping-stones for potential STEM majors” (p. 7). Halpern (2011) discusses adolescence as the period when differences in standardized math test achievement scores between male and female students appear. Feist (2006) found that students with talents in STEM were attracted to STEM early, well before college.

This study explores elementary and middle school students’ perceptions about computer science during their formative adolescent years. Eighty-four percent of females in this study believed that technology could be used in their career of choice. Sixty-seven percent of those females indicated belief that technology can help solve issues in their school, community, and/or world. The perceptions of urban K-8 female students can be a predictor of the number of women entering computer science fields, but without consistent access to technology, curricular, academic, and social support, the likelihood is not increased.

Summary

In Chapter V, the researcher analyzed the findings relative to the research questions in Chapter I and discussed the implications. The importance of computers science, role it plays in students’ lives, and gender associations were revealed through the data gathered. Chapter VI will present a summary of the thesis topic, conclusions, recommendations, and a reflection.

Chapter VI. Summary, Conclusions, Recommendations, and Reflection

Summary

Computer science has been widely discussed by educators, administrators, and manufacturers since the widespread technology initiative, popularized by the STEM/STEAM movement, became more than a buzz term. The charge to learn computer science, championed by former President Barack Obama in his 2013 endorsement alongside the popularity of coding through Code.org's Hour of Code events has moved the computer science initiative forward. President Obama's follow-up January 2016 federal call to action has kept learning computer science a part of important conversations in the field of Education. Experts predict that the number of jobs in the technology field will far outnumber the qualified labor force. Furthermore, the labor force in technology fields has seen imbalance in the number of qualified women in these fields versus qualified men. While the number of women graduating from four-year colleges and doctoral programs with computer science degrees has increased over the last few decades, a grave disproportion still exists (Appendix E).

The purpose of this research study was to address the following questions:

1. What role does computer science play in the lives of urban K-8 students?
2. What are the perceptions of urban K-8 students about computer science and its gender association?

3. Are the perceptions of urban K-8 female students a predictor of the number of women entering computer science fields due to the offering of computer science in K-8 learning environment?

Students' exposure to technology career pathways largely comes from family, friends, social settings, and teachers. If computer science/technology courses are not scheduled in school, the likelihood of exposure lessens, as focused instruction occurs mainly at school. Many organizations like Girls Who Code, Code.org, Latinas in STEM, Black Girls Code have increased exposure efforts through extracurricular activities/clubs, but pervasion in urban communities has not yet occurred. Without exposure to devices and Internet access, students in urban settings may not develop the confidence to pursue pathways to learning about technology areas such as computer science and consequently are less likely to succeed in technology fields. The initiative to include more females in technology fields is powered by varied groups of individuals. Some feminists vie for equality in access, while others vie for equity that allows women to occupy decision-making positions in boardrooms. All agree that the gender conversation must manifest into actual programs and initiatives that result in greater inclusion through greater access to technology. The technology industry as a whole is lacking minorities and women. Changes in current statistics in favor of females entering the field can best occur through adult championing of technology career pathways as viable options for females.

Conclusions

Through the analysis of data collected, it can be concluded that computer science should be integrated into the K-8 curriculum in urban schools. Computer science is not offered as a stand-alone course. Even with the success of the Hour of Code, just over half

of students surveyed had knowledge of the definition computer science. While some students in K-8 demonstrated awareness of computer science, the efforts to integrate computer science into classroom learning must dramatically increase so all students are just as aware as they are of math and English Language Arts. The majority of students perceived technology careers as male careers. Two-thirds of students used a computer three to five times per week. One third of students used a computing elementary and middle school due to students are not being exposed enough in school or at home. Social support factors, such as parental influence, teachers, and advisors will lead to a positive motivation toward technology career pathways, but the data suggest that computer science is still not given the attention necessary to become an option for students in urban K-8 schools.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends that stakeholders work to expose youth in urban areas to computer science through a variety of settings such as formal courses, clubs, and schoolwide events. Exposure to computer science at the elementary and middle school levels is critical. Computer science courses should be offered in every secondary school and there must be a concerted effort to encourage females to register. Principals must go beyond Computer Science Education week and lobby to district leaders like Curriculum and Instruction Directors for the inclusion of computer science coursework. Teachers must be instructed on the value of this coursework and provided with professional development teach them how to integrate computer science projects into classrooms. Code.org, for example, offers free professional development for educators. Many online content providers offer free coding activities and computer science curricula.

Recommendations for Classroom Teachers

Teachers have the most access to, and influence on, students during the school day. It is important for teachers to use this responsibility to positively impact students in scripted and unscripted ways. While it is imperative that teachers follow approved curriculum, introducing varied methods by which to teach the content is welcomed due to the necessity to differentiate and address multiple learning styles. Technology is meant to make the lives of people better. Teachers can echo this as the purpose for technology integration, create buy-in, and with a small learning curve, increase student exposure to computer science.

Recommendations for Parents/Guardians

Parents/guardians should ask questions at their child's school about computer science to find out whether the course is offered or if content can be offered in a club setting. If the school leader is not in the position to make these decisions, she or he can take the message to district leaders. Parents can offer to assist with the school's participation in the global Hour of Code. They can join the parent organization and learn more about the movement, career pathways, scholarships, internships/externships, and share the information amongst other parents and community members. Fong (2015) posits that the conversation about computer science at home is critical as well. Parents can learn with the child through entry-level activities and host coding parties at home or at community learning environments such as libraries and churches.

Recommendations for Schools

The researcher agrees with the NCWIT's recommendations for schools made in *Moving Beyond Computer Literacy*:

- Implement computer science classes. Provide rigorous and engaging computer science courses. Excellent curricula are available, as are additional units for integrating computing concepts into other content areas.
- Allow computer science to count toward graduation. Students' schedules are overcrowded, making electives difficult. Allow students to count computer science courses as math or science graduation credit.
- Make courses accessible for all. Recruit students who are underrepresented in computer science and use inclusive pedagogies in these courses.
- Improve teacher preparation and professional development. Expand teacher certification requirements to include computer science. Provide professional development for teachers who teach, or would like to teach, computer science.

(NCWIT, 2012, p. 2)

In order for computer science to be taken seriously as a course just as important as English Language Arts and Math, our policymakers and departments of education must treat it as a currency that all students need to have access to and one that has a high return on investment like other subjects do. Computer science is placed among electives, and while it may be seen as an enjoyable option for some, it must be framed as a necessary point of exposure along any career pathway for every student.

Recommendations for Future Researchers

The researcher recommends that future researchers explore how urban students' involvement in computer science classes may affect the performance of those students in other subject areas. Researchers may also replicate this study using high school students

in urban schools to ascertain how exposure to computer science in lower grades and high school affects career choices.

Reflection

For young females to be attracted to technology fields, they need to be shown how their innate interests complement work being conducted in technology fields, and how their contribution to this work can affect every aspect of daily and global life in the 21st Century. This needs to be demonstrated by families, teachers, community members, and global thought leaders that the conversation should no longer take place without female attendance and attendance in equal proportion. When females reach college campuses, it is critical that they see women role models in teaching and leadership positions. At the college level, inclusion should be less of a concerted effort and more of the natural order.

All stakeholders must contribute to a shared vision to give urban students access to computer science education. If the computer science pipeline is a one-size-fits-all pathway to a successful career in technology, that does not stimulate a racially and gender diverse population of learners, technology fields will actually experience a decline in female participation. The conversation must start early and there must be a seat for everyone at the discussion table, so the computer science field can enjoy equality and equity.

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Appendix A. IRB Approval Letter

Last Name Anderson

Project: Computer Science in Urban K-8

INITIAL, REVISED OR CONTINUATION

NOTICE OF IRB REVIEW AND APPROVAL

The project identified below, for which you requested review and approval by the NJCU Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Participants in Research, has now been reviewed and approved. This approval is based on the assumption that the materials you submitted to the NJCU IRB c/o Grants and Sponsored Programs contain a complete and accurate description of all the ways in which human subjects are involved in your research.

This approval is given with the following conditions:

1. That you will conduct the research according to the plans and protocol you submitted.
2. That you will immediately inform the IRB of any injuries to subjects that occur in the course of your research.
3. That you immediately inform the IRB of any problems that arise in the course of your research.
4. That you will immediately inform the IRB of any changes that you make in the protocol of the research.
5. That you will give each person who signs the consent document a copy of that document, if you are using such documents in your research.
6. That you will retain all signed consent documents for at least three years after the termination of the research.

Failure to comply with these conditions will result in the withdrawal of this approval.

Approved Not Approved

Name of Principal Investigator: Wilma Ann Anderson

Title of Project Computer Science in Urban K-8

Additional Conditions: n/a

Signed,

Brianne T. Kelly
NJCU Institutional Review Board Chair

03/02/16
Date

Appendix B. Letters to School Principals

Attn: XXXXXX XXXXXXXX
XXXXXXXXXX X. XXXX XXXX School - PS XX
XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX XXXXXXXX
XXXXXX XXXX, XX XXXXX

As per our previous discussions, I (the researcher) am a graduate student at New Jersey City University and I am currently working towards my master's degree in Educational Technology. I am in the process of writing my thesis entitled Computer Science in Urban K-8. In this study the researcher will attempt to survey students from PS XX and MS XX about their experience with computer science and their views on opportunities to enter computer technology fields.

Enclosed, please find a survey on white paper which should be completed by a random sampling of 100 students. All responses will be kept anonymous and confidential and the participants need not respond to all questions. Participation is voluntary.

I would appreciate the surveys completed and returned to me in a self-addressed, stamped envelope provided by February 1, 2016. If you have any questions or concerns, please feel free to contact me at [917-945-7697](tel:917-945-7697), Dr. Christopher Shamburg at [201-200-2546](tel:201-200-2546), or Dr. Beimnet Teclezghi, Chair of NJCU Institutional Review Board, at [201-200-3139](tel:201-200-3139) or email bteclezghi@njcu.edu.

Thank you for your time and effort. Your school will be mentioned in the acknowledgment section of my thesis and I would be happy to send you a copy of my summary on request.

Sincerely yours,

Wilma Ann Anderson
enclosures

Attn: Principal XXXXXXXXXX XXXXX
XXXX X. XXXXX School - MS XX
XX XXXXX XXXXXXX
XXXXXX XXXX, XX XXXXX

As per our previous discussions, I (the researcher) am a graduate student at New Jersey City University and I am currently working towards my master's degree in Educational Technology. I am in the process of writing my thesis entitled Computer Science in Urban K-8. In this study the researcher will attempt to survey students from PS XX and MS XX about their experience with computer science and their views on opportunities to enter computer technology fields.

Enclosed, please find a survey on white paper which should be completed by a random sampling of 100 students. All responses will be kept anonymous and confidential and the participants need not respond to all questions. Participation is voluntary.

I would appreciate the surveys completed and returned to me in a self-addressed, stamped envelope provided by February 1, 2016. If you have any questions or concerns, please feel free to contact me at 917-945-7697, Dr. Christopher Shamburg at 201-200-2546, or Dr. Beimnet Teclezghi, Chair of NJCU Institutional Review Board, at 201-200-3139 or email bteclezghi@njcu.edu.

Thank you for your time and effort. Your school will be mentioned in the acknowledgment section of my thesis and I would be happy to send you a copy of my summary on request.

Sincerely yours,

Wilma Ann Anderson
enclosures

Appendix C. School District Approval Letter

Office of the Superintendent

THE JERSEY CITY PUBLIC SCHOOLS
 346 Claremont Avenue
 Jersey City, New Jersey 07305
 Telephone: (201) 915-6210
 Fax: (201) 433-1783

Maryann Dickar, Ph.D.
Chief of Staff

June 6, 2016

Wilma Ann Anderson
 XX XXXXXXX XXXXXX
 XXXXXX XXXX XX XXXXX

Dear Ms. Anderson

Your request for permission to conduct "Computer Science in Urban K-8" in the Jersey City Public Schools has been granted. Your project entails administering an online survey to 100 randomly selected students in grades 3-5 at PS XX and 100 randomly selected students in grades 6-8 at MS XX.

Please show this letter to the administrators at schools you wish to work with and to any members of the Jersey City Public Schools community that you may engage as part of this study. Be aware that this letter permits you to conduct the research project you proposed but does not commit the Jersey City Public School District to support your work, nor does it commit any of its staff or community members to participate. All participants must willingly agree to be part of your study and must be free to withdraw from the study at any time. Your study may not interfere with the academic program or regular operation of the school. Interviews with school staff must be on their own time such as a lunch period or after or before work.

Please forward a copy of your final project to this office so that the District may learn from your work.

Sincerely,

Maryann Dickar, Ph D
 Chief of Staff
 Jersey City Public Schools

Appendix D. Informed Parental Consent Letter

MEMO

Dear Parent/Guardian:

I am a graduate student in the Educational Technology department at New Jersey City University. I will be conducting a research project under the supervision of Ella Rue as part of my master's thesis concerning how children living in urban areas of Jersey City, NJ perceive technology fields as via career choices. I am requesting permission for your child to participate in this research. The goal of the study is to determine entrance strategies to these fields, specifically Computer Science, through the public school system and community programming.

Each child will be invited to learn computer coding through weekly instruction and/or coding events such as The Hour of Code. They will complete one short survey about their views on Computer Science before and after instruction or the Computer Science event begins. Every child will be encouraged to participate, but if any child expresses a desire not to participate in the survey or instruction/coding event, s/he will be excused. To preserve each child's confidentiality, students will be referred to as S1, S2, etc. (Student1, Student2, etc.) to identify individuals. All data will be reported in terms of group results; individual results will not be reported.

Your decision whether or not to allow your child to participate in this study will have absolutely no effect on your child's standing in his/her class. At the conclusion of the study a summary of the group results will be made available to all interested parents. If you have any questions or concerns please contact me at 917-945-7697 or you may contact Christopher Shamburg at ext. 201-200-2546, or Mr. Beimnet Teclezghi, Chair of NJCU Institutional Review Board, at 201-200-3364 or email BTeclezghi@njcu.edu. Thank you.

Sincerely,

Wilma Ann Anderson

Please indicate whether or not you wish to have your child participate in this study by checking the appropriate statement below and returning this letter to your child's teacher by February 1, 2016.

I grant permission for my child _____ to participate in this study.

I do not grant permission for my child _____ to participate in this study.

Parent/Guardian Signature

Date

Signature of Principal Investigator

Date

Appendix E. Survey

Computer Science Questionnaire

DIRECTIONS: Answer all questions the best you can. (This is a voluntary survey.)

* Required

1. What is your gender? *

- female
 male

2. What is your race or ethnic heritage? *

- Latino/Hispanic
 African-American/Black (not of Hispanic origin)
 Native American
 Middle Eastern
 Asian
 Other:

3. What is your age? *

4. What grade are you in? *

5. Do you know what computer science is? *

- no
 yes

6. What do you think you would learn in computer science class? Select all that apply. *

- A. programming

- B. how computers work
- C. advanced computer use
- D. networking
- E. computer repair
- F. Internet use
- G. how to use social media (like Facebook)
- H. research

7. Is there an adult in your life who works with computers or other types of technology? *

- A. no
- B. yes

8. How often do you use a computer at your school? *

- never
- 1 or 2 times a week
- 3 or 4 times a week
- 5 times a week

9. "In my opinion, learning computer science is _____ the required courses like Math, Science, Social Studies, and English." *

- not as important as
- just as important as
- more important than

10. Do the computer science opportunities offered in your school include any of the following elements? Select all that apply. *

- A. computer graphics
- B. creating websites
- C. computer programming and coding robotics / artificial intelligence
- D. creating a video or online games creating applications (apps)
- E. There are no opportunities at my school

11. Do you think technology jobs like programming computers are a male kind of job or female kind of job? *

- A. male
- B. female

12. Is there a computer, cell phone or tablet at home that you use to access the Internet? *

- A. no
- B. yes

13. What do you want to be when you grow up? *

14. Do you think computer science can be used in that career? *

- A. no
 B. yes

15. Do you think technology can help solve any issues in your school, community, and/or world? *

- A. no
 B. yes

16. If you answered "yes," how can technology be used to make improvements?

Submit

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Appendix F. Degrees in Information and Computer Sciences

Table 325.35. Degrees in computer and information sciences conferred by postsecondary institutions, by level of degree and sex of student: 1970-71 through 2014-15

Year	Bachelor's degrees					Master's degrees			Doctor's degrees		
	Total		Males	Females	Females as a percent of total	Total	Males	Females	Total	Males	Females
	Number	Annual percent change									
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1970-71	2,388	†	2,064	324	13.6	1,588	1,424	164	128	125	3
1971-72	3,402	42.5	2,941	461	13.6	1,977	1,752	225	167	155	12
1972-73	4,304	26.5	3,664	640	14.9	2,113	1,888	225	196	181	15
1973-74	4,756	10.5	3,976	780	16.4	2,276	1,983	293	198	189	9
1974-75	5,033	5.8	4,080	953	18.9	2,299	1,961	338	213	199	14
1975-76	5,652	12.3	4,534	1,118	19.8	2,603	2,226	377	244	221	23
1976-77	6,407	13.4	4,876	1,531	23.9	2,798	2,332	466	216	197	19
1977-78	7,201	12.4	5,349	1,852	25.7	3,038	2,471	567	196	181	15
1978-79	8,719	21.1	6,272	2,447	28.1	3,055	2,480	575	236	206	30
1979-80	11,154	27.9	7,782	3,372	30.2	3,647	2,883	764	240	213	27
1980-81	15,121	35.6	10,202	4,919	32.5	4,218	3,247	971	252	227	25
1981-82	20,267	34.0	13,218	7,049	34.8	4,935	3,625	1,310	251	230	21
1982-83	24,565	21.2	15,641	8,924	36.3	5,321	3,813	1,508	262	228	34
1983-84	32,439	32.1	20,416	12,023	37.1	6,190	4,379	1,811	251	225	26
1984-85	39,121	20.6	24,737	14,384	36.8	7,101	5,064	2,037	248	223	25
1985-86	42,337	8.2	27,208	15,129	35.7	8,070	5,658	2,412	344	299	45
1986-87	39,767	-6.1	25,962	13,805	34.7	8,481	5,985	2,496	374	322	52
1987-88	34,651	-12.9	23,414	11,237	32.4	9,197	6,726	2,471	428	380	48
1988-89	30,560	-11.8	21,143	9,417	30.8	9,414	6,775	2,639	351	466	85
1989-90	27,347	-10.5	19,159	8,188	29.9	9,677	6,960	2,717	627	534	93
1990-91	25,159	-8.0	17,771	7,388	29.4	9,324	6,563	2,761	676	584	92
1991-92	24,821	-1.3	17,685	7,136	28.7	9,655	6,980	2,675	772	669	103
1992-93	24,519	-1.2	17,606	6,913	28.2	10,353	7,557	2,796	805	689	116
1993-94	24,527	#	17,528	6,999	28.5	10,568	7,836	2,732	810	685	125
1994-95	24,737	0.9	17,684	7,053	28.5	10,595	7,805	2,790	887	726	161
1995-96	24,506	-0.9	17,757	6,749	27.5	10,579	7,729	2,850	869	743	126
1996-97	25,422	3.7	18,527	6,895	27.1	10,513	7,526	2,987	857	721	136
1997-98	27,829	9.5	20,372	7,457	26.8	11,765	8,343	3,422	858	718	140
1998-99	30,552	9.8	22,289	8,263	27.0	12,843	8,866	3,977	806	656	150
1999-2000	37,788	23.7	27,185	10,603	28.1	14,990	9,978	5,012	779	648	131
2000-01	44,142	16.8	31,923	12,219	27.7	16,911	11,195	5,716	768	632	136
2001-02	50,365	14.1	36,462	13,903	27.6	17,173	11,447	5,726	752	581	171
2002-03	57,433	14.0	41,950	15,483	27.0	19,509	13,267	6,242	816	648	168
2003-04	59,488	3.6	44,585	14,903	25.1	20,143	13,868	6,275	909	709	200
2004-05	54,111	-9.0	42,125	11,986	22.2	18,416	13,136	5,280	1,119	905	214
2005-06	47,480	-12.3	37,705	9,775	20.6	17,055	12,470	4,585	1,416	1,109	307
2006-07	42,170	-11.2	34,342	7,828	18.6	16,232	11,985	4,247	1,595	1,267	328
2007-08	38,476	-8.8	31,694	6,782	17.6	17,087	12,513	4,574	1,698	1,333	375
2008-09	37,992	-1.3	31,213	6,779	17.8	17,907	13,063	4,844	1,580	1,226	354
2009-10	39,593	4.2	32,414	7,179	18.1	17,955	13,019	4,936	1,599	1,250	349
2010-11	43,066	8.8	35,477	7,589	17.6	19,516	14,010	5,506	1,588	1,267	321
2011-12	47,406	10.1	38,796	8,610	18.2	20,925	15,132	5,793	1,698	1,332	366
2012-13	50,961	7.5	41,874	9,087	17.8	22,782	16,539	6,243	1,834	1,480	354
2013-14	55,271	8.5	45,320	9,951	18.0	24,514	17,472	7,042	1,982	1,566	416
2014-15	59,581	7.8	48,840	10,741	18.0	31,474	21,892	9,582	1,998	1,548	450
Percent change											
2004-05 to 2009-10	-26.8	†	-23.1	-40.1	†	-2.5	-0.9	-6.5	42.9	38.1	63.1
2009-10 to 2014-15	50.5	†	50.7	49.6	†	75.3	68.2	94.1	25.0	23.8	28.9

†Not applicable.
#Rounds to zero.
NOTE: Data are for postsecondary institutions participating in Title IV federal financial aid programs. Some data have been revised from previously published figures.
SOURCE: U.S. Department of Education, National Center for Education Statistics, Higher Education General Information Survey (HEGIS), "Degrees and Other Formal Awards Conferred" surveys, 1970-71 through 1985-86; Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System (IPEDS), "Completions Survey" (IPEDS-C-87-95); and IPEDS Fall 2000 through Fall 2015, Completions component. (This table was prepared January 2017.)